

D1.1 Literature review report: The role of data in the R&I policy cycle

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Executive Summary

The present literature review found a large body of studies and publications about innovation indicators, but only few insights about the role of indicators in the policy life cycle. Further, where the role of indicators for policymaking are explored, they are mainly discussed in the context of climate and health policies, with limited studies on indicators for innovation policy.

Indicators play different roles in the various phases of the policy life cycle. It is important to note that the common development of indicators is an important step in policy formulation. The development of legitimizing innovation policy from market to system failure, and most recently mission orientation and the accompanying focus on demand-side-oriented policy instruments, generate new demand for innovation indicators as current indicators are inadequate. There are many potential opportunities and threats of failure from the very beginning of the innovation indicator development process (from deciding on the use of innovation indicators) to their impacts along the innovation policy cycle, for instance, the misuse and misinterpretation. It is recommended that such identified threats are considered in the further phases of indicator development within the EURITO project. Future innovation indicators based on new data sources to be developed by EURITO must fulfil several requirements including RITO to gain acceptance among innovation policymakers.

Such recommendations and findings highlighted in the present report will be considered when scaling up and implementing the selected innovation pilot indicators. Overall, the findings of the literature review will guide EURITO to develop indicators, by not only fulfilling the RITO criteria in the narrower sense but also to be valued by policymakers in general.

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1. Introduction

Policymaking is complex and dynamic, where outcomes are constantly influenced by many external factors, e.g. society, industry, but also science and technology. It is crucial to have the correct information and relevant evidence. They help to explain the policy environment, to identify the available policy options and to select the most effective and efficient instrument for reaching certain objectives and goals, including insight into its detailed specifications. Evidence comes in many forms and can range from real experiences, histories over expert opinions to results of structured experiments, simulations and other scientific approaches codified in the literature and eventually data and indicators. The legitimacy of sources of evidence have changed over the centuries, with quantitative sources taking precedence in recent times. New data sources driven by new technologies in big data and machine learning have become recently available in the last few years for decision makers not only in industry but also for policymakers. These new sources of evidence have an impact on evidence-based policy making.

Innovation policy, in particular, is highly complex and dynamic, driven by new insights in science and technology, but also changes in markets and companies. Consequently, timeliness of information is more crucial for innovation policy compared to policies with longer policy life cycles. The very multidimensional phenomena of innovation also require multiple data sources and indicators, which further challenge policymaking related to innovation. At the same time, new data sources allow the development of complementary and new indicators. They represent opportunities to improve the measurement of innovation along its various dimensions, but also over time and space. Yet, this also poses a challenge to policymaking: the adequate selection and interpretation of these indicators require additional capabilities of actors making decisions along the policy life cycle.

The objective of this deliverable is to provide a robust foundation of the use of data and indicators along the policy life cycle with a specific focus on innovation policy. We aim to identify the evidence needs of research and innovation policymakers along the policy cycle, from agenda setting through policy design to implementation and evaluation. These findings will inform the selection of potential data pilots that address policy needs related to research and innovation policy while harnessing complementarities with existing projects and initiatives.

To review the literature about the needs of policymakers for research and innovation policy, we conducted a broad search in the Web of Science, Google Scholar and Scopus. We identified almost one thousand sources, which have been screened for their relevance. After the selection of the relevant sources, we based our review on roughly one hundred sources, mainly scientific papers, but also research reports and books. Further, we contacted some of the most active authors and asked for most relevant studies. From both the literature review and the feedback we received from experts, revealed that the role of data and indicators along the policy life cycle relevant for innovation policy has not been investigated in-depth. Therefore, we expanded our search to studies and investigations about the role of indicators in policymaking in general. Insights from the use of indicators for environmental and health policies provided valuable findings to feed into recommendations for the next steps of EURITO,

to avoid mistakes in the development and implementation of innovation indicators, such as producing indicators without use or having no influence on policymaking.

The remainder of the literature review is structured as follows. In the second chapter, we introduce the policy life cycle in general and various roles of indicators. The third chapter is devoted to innovation policy starting with the various rationales and the numerous innovation policy instruments. The fourth presents the various traditional innovation indicators with their advantages and disadvantages for innovation policy making. In the fifth chapter, the evidence needs of policymakers in general followed by the role of innovation indicators in innovation policy are presented. This chapter concludes with the desired attributes of innovation indicators from the perspective of innovation policymakers. New data sources for innovation policy are presented in chapter six. Finally, the seventh chapter concludes the literature review with the major findings relevant for the next tasks and Work Packages of EURITO.

2. Evidence-based policymaking

2.1 The Policy Life Cycle

Policy-making is a complex mechanism. Observing the full effect of an implemented policy might take years and its success may depend on a variety of factors and unique cultural contexts. Furthermore, unexpected internal or external factors might drastically affect the success or failure of a policy. Though one cannot consider all possible effects and eventualities, having the correct information and relevant evidence regarding a policy choice could prove pivotal. The importance associated with evidence in policymaking has led to the development of evidence-informed policymaking or ‘Evidence-Based Policy’. From agenda setting to adoption and finally evaluation, the use of evidence plays a central role in the policy cycle as well as being vital to impact assessments. Indeed, evidence can help explain the policy environment and options, the various effects of different policies and what path to take to reach a certain objective or goal (Shaxson 2005).

Figure 1: Conceptual Model for Evidence-Informed Policy Formulation and Implementation (Source: based on Strehlenert et al. 2015)

However, the inherently complex nature of policymaking raises challenges for evidence-informed policymaking, including issues of bounded rationality, subjectivity and robustness (see Boavide et al. 2016, Shaxson 2005). Though no ideal formula or model of policymaking exists which take into consideration all variables and possibilities, as well as outlining objective proposals, certain issues can be mitigated to ensure that the evidence is more robust.

In general, evidence is related to scientific output from all research ranging from the hard to the soft sciences (Boavide et al. 2016). However, evidence tailored to public policy becomes more selective as a tool for argumentation in proving or disproving a point. Evidence comes in many forms and can be "...indicators, historical facts, statistics, and results of experiments, texts, quotes from secondary sources, real experiences or histories, or opinions of individuals in one field (*ibid.*)". Context also plays a vital role in the characteristics of evidence, with some forms of evidence exhibiting high external validity (i.e. they can be taken up easily across different contexts) and others being heavily context-dependent. For example, research on the effect of a particular drug on the human body is likely to be replicable and valid across most cultural, geographical and ideological boundaries. For policy however, context matters a great deal to whether a particular type of evidence is valid, and "...evidence can range from numerical data to ethical/moral interpretations expressing values, attitudes and perceptions of stakeholders and other decision makers (*ibid.*)".

The case of innovation policy, which is inadequately addressed within policy cycle research, is analysed below.

2.2 The Role of Indicators in the Policy Life Cycle

Indicators play, depending on their type, different roles in the policy life cycle. According to Lehtonen (2015), descriptive indicators are used to monitor and describe the initial situation followed by analytical indicators deployed for its analysis. In the programming and realization stage or the policy formulation following the diagnosis, indicators are used for prognosis of expected or potential developments, but also for overall programming and planning as well as medium- and long-term goals. In this sense, indicators are participatory; both as input to participatory policymaking and as a tool for framing policy problems. In addition, indicators can serve for the translation of broad policy aims into specific goals, but also as 'vehicles' carrying specific visions (Lehtonen 2017). For the comparison of potential impacts of different policy options, indicators can be deployed for ex-ante impact assessments. Finally, control indicators might be used for the description of the final situation after the implementation of the decided policy intervention complemented by impact indicators for the reflection of its outcome within formal assessment methods and eventually effectiveness indicators for assessing its effectiveness.

We will use the above mentioned conceptual framework for the analysis of the use of innovation indicators within the innovation policy life cycle.

3. Innovation Policy

3.1 Rationale for Innovation policy

Innovation is a central focal point in contemporary societies where extensive policies are implemented with the goal to foster economic growth. Innovation is perceived to strengthen a country's economy, help with a nation's development, create jobs and increase the welfare of citizens (e.g. Arundel and Hollanders 2005, European Commission 2018, Dodgson et al. 2011, Grupp and Mogege 2004). It therefore comes as no surprise that the European Union (EU) has consistently set itself innovation goals and objectives such as those contained within the Lisbon Strategy (Arundel and Hollanders 2005) and Europe's 2020 flagship initiative 'Innovation Union' (European Commission 2013). Furthermore, innovation policy has broadened in scope in recent years from purely economic objectives to considering issues such as the social impact of innovation and to what extent it is sustainable or responsible (Gault 2011, Wieczorek and Hekkert 2012, Monsonís-Payá 2017). It should be noted that innovation policy - as with all policy - has a variety of stakeholders and is likely often more strongly influenced by the political process and opinions of policymakers than by research. Nonetheless, the shape and form of policy chosen to be implemented in fostering innovation depends largely on which economic theoretical perspective is most pervasive.

In mainstream neoclassical economics, innovation is limited to referring to research and inventions. The innovative process is perceived to be sequential (linear) (Chaminade and Edquist 2010). Moreover, innovation is roughly equated with knowledge creation with little consideration given to the actual innovative process from research to the final product (*ibid.*). According to neoclassical economics, the reason for policy intervention is linked to 'market failures' due to knowledge spillovers created by the innovation process and the public good character of knowledge being the basis for innovations. This leads to underinvestment in R&D by economies and private actors, i.e. to a less than optimal allocation of resources in R&D and consequently, rendering the system inefficient.

In classical economics, equilibrium is reached when information and competition are perfect and subsequently, profits can be maximised. However, if "...this fails to be the case, governments should intervene to mitigate non-desired externalities and asymmetries in information, correct inefficient market structures or eliminate the barriers to entry (*ibid.*, p.98)." As a result, according to the perspective of market failures, viable investment areas include large projects such as in energy research and innovation. Here, "...the public rate of return was expected to be high, the barriers to entry were significant and the externalities were also assumed to be sizeable (*ibid.*."

The problem with neoclassical theory in explaining innovation and subsequently, its use in innovation policy, is that it lacks specificity and practical applications. By focusing on economic phenomena, like as incomplete information, externalities and increasing returns, leading to failures it is too general and has difficulties outlining in which particular areas and to what extent innovation policy should intervene.

The systems of innovation (SI) approach mainly developed in parallel by Freeman (1982, 1987) and Lundvall (1985, 2007) can be traced to economic evolutionary theory as well as institutional theories (see Hekkert et al. 2007). The SI approach materialized

from the observed limits of neoclassical theory pertaining to the analysis of innovation mechanisms (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). Unlike the neoclassical theory, SI theory emphasises that companies do not innovate alone and independently but rather, within a system engaging with other organisations and institutions on a regional, national and global level. The perception of the SI approach of contextual and interactive innovation mechanisms has had a large impact on the framing, form, tools and target of innovation policy.

Figure 2: Managing National Systems of Innovation (Source: OECD 1999)

Unlike neoclassical theory, the SI approach perceives innovation to emerge spontaneously and focuses on the interactions between various organisations. In the SI approach, 'the failures' or more aptly put 'the problems' that innovation policy aims to tackle are termed 'systemic problems'. These problems are perceived to compromise the smooth operation of the innovation system. Thus, systemic problems provide the rationale for policy interventions and within the SI framework, innovation policy should be complementary to market forces and not competing. Some examples of systemic problems include those associated with a lack of infrastructure and investment (transport, technical institutes and university excellence), lock-in problems within a particular technological system or paradigm as well as institutional problems ranging from regulation or rules to institutional social and political cultures (Hekkert et al. 2007).

The SI approach has also come under criticism. Firstly, the perceived 'quasi-static' nature of the analysis of innovation systems focusing on the comparison between existing systems instead of understanding the dynamics within specific systems. Secondly, that the focus and explanatory strength of the SI approach is on the macro level, i.e. institutions, and not on the micro level, i.e. the entrepreneurs as the major drivers of innovations and consequently innovation systems ignoring or even violating institutional frameworks (*ibid.*).

There is one aspect where the market failure approach has been argued to have more explanatory power than the systems approach—in outlining an optimum that guides policy action (Swann 2010), which is also connected with the lack of adequate indicators (Chaminade and Edquist 2010). Nonetheless, the SI approach has many strengths and has been adopted by various governments in their approach to innovation policy (see Mytelka and Smith 2002).

	Mainstream	Evolutionary theory and Systems of Innovation approach
Underlying assumptions	Equilibrium Perfect information	Non-equilibrium Asymmetric information
Focus	Allocation for resources for invention Individuals	Interaction in innovation processes Networks and Framework conditions
Main policy	Science Policy (Research)	Innovation policy
Main rationale	Market failure	Systemic Problems
Government intervenes to (examples)	Provide public goods Mitigate externalities Reduce barriers to entry Eliminate inefficient market structures	Solve problems in the system or to facilitate creating of the new systems. Induce changes in the supporting structure for innovation: support the creating and development of institutions and organizations & support networking Facilitate transition and avoid lock-in
Main strengths of innovation policies designed under each paradigm	Clarity and simplicity Analysis based on long time series of science-based indicators	Context specific Involvement of all policies related to innovation Holistic conception of the innovation process
Main weaknesses of innovation policies designed under each paradigm	Linear model of innovation Framework conditions are not explicitly considered in the model (e.g. institutional framework)	Difficult to implement in practice Lack of indicators for the analysis of the SI and evaluation of SI policies

Table 1: Neoclassical versus SI approach to science and innovation policy (Source: Chaminade and Edquist 2010)

3.2 Mission-Oriented Policy Framework

One's ideology, not only in terms of political affiliations but most significantly, one's perception of what the relationship should be between the state and market hugely impacts the policymaking process. Indeed, within the neo-liberal ideological perspective often prevalent in the United States, the state is depicted as cumbersome, too large and wasteful, whereas the private sector is perceived as efficient and the source of economic growth and innovation (Martin 2016). This tradition is connected to the framework of 'market failures'. In many European countries the relationship between the state and market as well as the relationship with innovation is seen differently (the UK is a possible exception).

Advocates of the neo-liberal laissez-faire ideological perspectives may be accused of suffering from a selective worldview. Indeed, in the US, the benefits from state funding for the development of modern practises and technology cannot be underestimated. From pharmaceuticals benefiting from funding from National Institutes of Health, to

microchips (Department of Defense, NASA), Apple and PCs (SBIR), and the Internet (DARPA) to name but a few examples, the US government has been a strong driver of innovation. This leads to Mazzucato's (2013) proposition that the state should not be perceived in a passive framework rectifying market failure but rather, as the 'entrepreneurial state' taking risks and investing in innovation. In terms of innovation policy, this 'entrepreneurial state' exists within the 'Mission-Oriented policy framework' (Mazzucato and Penna 2016).

To begin, "Innovation policy must build on the key characteristics of how innovation comes about: it is uncertain; cumulative; and collective (*ibid.* p. 7)". Mission-oriented policy-making is connected to a systems perspective, where a range of instruments is used across sectors with a particular course in view of the economy. Four subsystems are outlined within the national systems of innovation: public policy and public funding, private finance and private funding, research and education as well as production and innovation. Furthermore, mission-oriented policies are built on strong relationships among stakeholders, large amounts of foresight in outlining specific strategies as well as a state that accepts risks and the ability to move forward and learn from mistakes (*ibid.* p.8).

3.3 Policy Instruments

Policy instruments are best described as ways for governments to instigate change, but also conversely, mitigate against potential changes, e.g. using protectionist measures against globalization. The choice of policy instruments adopted depends on a variety of factors including what the specific aim of the innovation policy is, the national context in terms of social and political interests, sensitivities, as well as the state to market relationship and the ideologies of those in power. Furthermore, the choice of policy instruments depends largely on the identified problem and most importantly, what the underlying reasons behind the problem are that needs to be tackled (Borrás and Edquist 2016).

Problems are identified through various measurements—most notably, innovation surveys and indicators. There are three types of policy instruments: regulatory instruments, economic/financial instruments and soft instruments. This is what can be termed "...the 'sticks', the 'carrots' and the 'sermons' of public policy instruments" (Borrás and Edquist 2013, p. 1515). Regulatory instruments are backed by the rule of law and compliance is obligatory. Economic/ financial instruments are incentives (e.g. subsidies) or disincentives (e.g. taxes or fees) promoting certain pathways or activities. Soft instruments do not require compliance and are voluntary such as with the adoption of certain standards. The selection of policy instruments is linked to various activities in the innovation system (see Box 1). The activities are categorized within four sections by Borrás and Edquist (2013):

- Provision of knowledge inputs to the innovation process (e.g. R&D)
- Demand-side activities (e.g. quality requirements)
- Provisions of constituents for systems of innovation (e.g. regulation)
- Support services for innovating firms (e.g. incubation activities)

Instruments can be further differentiated based on whether they cater to the supply or demand side of innovation (Edler and Fagerberg 2017). Table 2 outlines Edler and Fagerberg's (2017) depiction of policy instruments, whilst considering the

differentiation between the supply and demand side of innovation. Whereas the majority are from the supply side, some are from the demand side or both (e.g. regulation and standardization).

Innovation policy instruments		Overall orientation		Goals						
		Supply	Demand	Increase R&D	Skills	Access to expertise	Improve systemic capability, complementarity	Enhance demand for innovation	Improve framework	Improve discourse
1	Fiscal incentives for R&D	●●●		●●●	●○○					
2	Direct support to firm R&D and innovation	●●●		●●●						
3	Policies for training and skills	●●●			●●●					
4	Entrepreneurship policy	●●●				●●●				
5	Technical services and advice	●●●				●●●				
6	Cluster policy	●●●					●●●			
7	Policies to support collaboration	●●●		●○○		●○○	●●●			
8	Innovation network policies	●●●					●●●			
9	Private demand for innovation		●●●					●●●		
10	Public procurement policies		●●●	●○○				●●●		
11	Pre-commercial procurement	●○○	●●●	●○○				●●●		
12	Innovation inducement prizes	●●○	●●○	●●○				●●○		
13	Standards	●●○	●●○					●○○	●●●	
14	Regulation	●●○	●●○					●○○	●●●	
15	Technology foresight	●●○	●●○							●●●

Notes: ●●● = major relevance, ●●○ = moderate relevance, and ●○○ = minor relevance to the overall orientation and stated innovation policy goals of the listed innovation policy instruments.

Table 2: Taxonomy of innovation policy instruments (Source: Edler & Fagerberg 2017)

Box 1 Key activities in systems of innovation

- (i) Provision of knowledge inputs to the innovation process
 - (1) Provision of R&D results and, thus, creation of new knowledge, primarily in engineering, medicine and natural sciences.
 - (2) Competence building, for example, through individual learning (educating and training the labor force for innovation and R&D activities) and organizational learning. This includes formal learning as well as informal learning.
- (ii) Demand-side activities
 - (3) Formation of new product markets.
 - (4) Articulation of new product quality requirements emanating from the demand side.
- (iii) Provision of constituents for SIs
 - (5) Creating and changing organizations needed for developing new fields of innovation. Examples include enhancing entrepreneurship to create new firms and intrapreneurship to diversify existing firms; and creating new research organizations, policy organizations, etc.
 - (6) Networking through markets and other mechanisms, including interactive learning among different organizations (potentially) involved in the innovation processes. This implies integrating new knowledge elements developed in different spheres of the SI and coming from outside with elements already available in the innovating firms.
 - (7) Creating and changing institutions—for example, patent laws, tax laws, environment and safety regulations, R&D investment routines, cultural norms, etc.—that influence innovating organizations and innovation processes by providing incentives for and removing obstacles to innovation.
- (iv) Support services for innovating firms
 - (8) Incubation activities such as providing access to facilities and administrative support for innovating efforts.
 - (9) Financing of innovation processes and other activities that may facilitate commercialization of knowledge and its adoption.
 - (10) Provision of consultancy services relevant for innovation processes, for example, technology transfer, commercial information, and legal advice.

Source: Edquist (2011).

When considering the ten activities that influence the form and types of an innovation policy according to Edquist (2011), it should be noted that different areas of government hold the power of using certain policy instruments. Furthermore, from an activity perspective in an innovation system, both demand and supply-side instruments should be given equal consideration, where traditionally (within science policies) supply-side instruments have been the dominant focus. Borrás and Edquist (2013) argue that more demand-side innovation instruments are required such as Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI), where an order by the state of a non-existent product necessitates innovation. The authors further state that in designing policy instruments one should look at their relationship with the ten activities where instruments are often combined (i.e. policy mix) to tackle a specific problem. How the various innovation policy instruments and activities in the IS interact is outlined in Table 3. However, policy mixes not only combine different instruments of innovation policy in a narrower sense but can be much broader including policies mainly targeting other policy objectives (Meissner et al. 2017), like the protection of the environment.

However, it should be reiterated that in reality not all choices of policy instruments are made from objective research but are influenced by the political environment.

Stakeholder interests or common limitations such as time constraints exist, where for example previous policies are simply prolonged even if they might not be the most suitable anymore.

			Activities in the innovation system									
			Provision of R&D	Competence building	New product markets	Articulation of quality requirements	Creating and changing organizations	Interactive learning	Creating and changing institutions	Incubation activities	Financing innovation	Consultancy services
Type of policy instruments	Regulation	Intellectual property rights	X		X				X	X		
		Competition law	X	X		X			X			
		Ethical regulations	X						X			X
	Economic transfer	‘En block’ support of R&D	X	X	X						X	
		Competitive funding of R&D	X								X	
		Tax exemptions Public	X	X	X						X	
		Public procurement for innovation				X	X	X				
		‘En block’ support for innovation-promotion					X	X		X		X
	Soft instruments	Voluntary standardization				X			X			
		Public-private partnerships	X	X		X	X	X				
		Codes of conduct					X		X			

Table 3: Activities in the innovation system and type of policy instruments (Source: Borrás and Edquist 2013)

4. Measurement of Innovation

The OECD's creation of the Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) indicators was one of the initial measures taken to collect, outline and compare the level of innovation and technology between countries. Beginning in the 1970s many nations then began collecting their own STI performance measures.

To provide an overview, the innovation cube uses three distinct dimensions to categorise innovation indicators, i.e. the unit of analysis, the phase within the innovation process and the degree of user-drivenness or supply-sided technology push vs. demand-sided market pull. An alternative way to provide an overview of specific science and technology indicators and their interrelations along the science and technology dimension is presented below in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Innovation cube (Source: Sindi website adapted from VTT symposium on service innovation 2011)

In accordance with the framework outlined in the OECD Oslo Manual providing guidelines for collecting and interpreting innovation data (OECD 2005), the OECD adapted innovation surveys in the framework of the IS approach (Gault 2011, 2018). In the EU, the Community Innovation Survey (CIS) and the Innovation Barometer are two key approaches to collecting innovation data in the Member States since decades. Moreover, “[a]rguably the primary impact of the Oslo Manual’s implementation has been the acceptance of non-linear models of innovation under the systems of innovation broad heading” (Cust, 2008, p.9). Information about innovation processes and successes is often gathered through surveys whereas register-related indicators are constructed that attempt to explain the innovation environment.

New developments in science and technology often pose challenges for the existing regulatory framework or call for the creation of new regulatory frameworks, but also for new economic instruments of innovation policy complemented by voluntary soft instruments. The dynamics and changes in science and technology can be identified and traced by different indicators. These indicators allow for the creation of comparisons over time between scientific and technological fields, between countries, and across organisations. The most important science and technology indicators are publications in scientific journals and patents. The former indicator provides some sense of the activities in basic research (although peer-reviewed publications can also

include findings from applied research), whereas the latter reflects the performance in applied research and development. Technical standards are an emerging form of indicator, which are released by formal standardisation bodies (see Figure 4). Since standardisation is a kind of industry self-regulation, it may be complementary—or even act as a substitute—to the regulatory framework following the differentiation between regulation and soft instruments proposed by Borrás and Edquist (2013).

Figure 4: Science and technology indicators (Source: based on Blind 2008)

4.1 Traditional innovation indicators

4.1.1 R&D

R&D can be measured as the percentage of people employed to carry out R&D in a firm or, more commonly, in terms of expenditure. R&D measurements are the most prevalent innovation indicator and have been collected since the 1950s. They have been integral to the OECD's attempt to measure and compare innovation by harmonising innovation data collection and research (OECD Frascati Manual 2015). R&D indicators help to compare countries, sectors, industries and even companies. Recently, R&D process and product efforts can also be differentiated. This is an important distinction in terms of the analysis of innovation on a company's performance as the product innovation plays a central role to a company's financial performance and future (Kleinknecht and Montfort 2002).

Despite their widespread adoption, there are important weaknesses in using R&D indicators for innovation analysis. R&D is an input measurement for

innovation, which says nothing about innovation itself in terms of output. Indeed, the R&D measurements do not necessarily equate to innovation and the commercialisation of new products or processes. Furthermore, R&D is often perceived as being biased toward manufacturing industries (Kleinknecht and Montfort 2002) and is not the only input for innovation (e.g. trial production or market analysis) where for example, user-driven innovation can also emerge (Gault and Hippel 2009). In addition, the traditional R&D surveys under-represent informal R&D or those investments undertaken by smaller firms as opposed to innovation surveys, which ask more simplified questions about R&D. This problem can be traced to the historical context of R&D research and innovation, which emerged at a time where large firms and laboratories existed and where the state was financing large-scale industrial projects for economic, political and ideological reasons (e.g. in the cold war).

R&D analysis is also biased towards the high-tech sector. This point is illustrated by Santamaría et al. (2009), who investigated innovation within the low-and-medium-technology (LMT) industries. Looking at Spanish manufacturing firms, they attempt to outline how the innovative process within these LMT firms are based on non-formalised R&D. Their results indicate that "...non-R&D activities such as design, the use of advanced machinery and training are crucial to understanding the innovation process of any firm (Santamaría et al. 2009, p. 507)" and particularly important for LMT industries.

4.1.2 Scientific Publications

Many countries throughout the world including, for example, Australia, Spain, Norway, Denmark use performance indicators based on scientific publications to frame the allocation of resources in the Higher Education Sector (Butler 2004, Sivertsen 2010). Though this approach provides the benefits of outlining innovative ideas emerging from academia as well as the connections and causality through bibliometric analysis between them, there are certain limitations.

One of the most notable limitations of bibliometric indicators in line with Goodhart's law, which states that when a measure becomes in itself the goal, it ceases to be a good measure (Feller 2013, Freeman and Soete 2009). Indeed, using the number of publications as a metric through which to make funding allocation decisions can have a negative impact on the quality of publications and thus diminishes its calibre as an innovation indicator. To counter this shortcoming, research funders have begun expanding beyond a narrow focus of number of publications to include metrics such as international co-publications and citation counts normalised by field of science.

Nevertheless, recently, Simeth and Raffo (2013) investigate the scientific publications of companies and reveal a strong correlation with their patenting activities, which push their innovation and eventually their economic performance (Simeth and Cincera 2016).

4.1.3 Patents

Patents are a 'throughput' measurement of innovation (Janger et al. 2017). They are deemed useful in terms of providing some format for quantifying

innovation, are easily accessible through large databases, and can be analysed over a long period. Furthermore, as some patents are far more often implemented in innovative technologies and products than others, a simple comparison of the number of patents would provide a misleading perspective on innovative activity and hence the problem can be rectified with citation analysis.

However, the use of patents as an indicator has serious limitations— most importantly, not all innovations are based on, or result in, patents. As a consequence, similar to R&D indicators, patents only provide a narrow, limited view of the innovation environment. In addition, Cohen et al. (2000) reveal the reasons why companies decide deliberately not to file patents. The value distribution of granted patents is highly skewed (Harhoff et al. 1999) as a significant share of patents is never used (Torrise et al. 2016). Some companies file patents without using them for their innovation simply to stop their competition from using it (Blind et al. 2006). In addition, some patents only provide a slight improvement to a previous innovation or invention with very little financial benefits and other patents represent radical changes and the issues arise whether citation analysis is able to accommodate these large differences (Blind et al. 2009). Moreover, patenting activity varies across sectors depending on the imitation costs of a product, e.g. the low cost for imitation in the pharmaceutical industry makes patents much more attractive. Firm size also plays an important role in patenting activity, with smaller firms having a threshold issue in terms of patents, i.e. they are less likely to apply for one patent. However, once one patent has been filed, firms go on to patent much more (Kleinknecht et al. 2002). Collaborative R&D between firms also results in a larger amount of patenting (Kleinknecht et al. 2002).

Overall, using patents as a measure of innovation results in large measurement challenges, where innovation is often either underestimated or overestimated. Since both the structure of the economy and its innovation activities have become much more centralised in services, the overlap between innovations and patents as indicated by Figure 5 has become smaller due to the difficulty of applying for patents related to innovations in services. Consequently, the indicators established in the last decade have a stronger focus on capturing innovative activity in services, for example through trademarks and designs.

Figure 5: Patents and Innovation (Source: based on Grupp 1998)

4.1.4 Trademarks

Trademarks can play a significant role in a firm’s business model and strategy. Trademarks allow a firm to protect the reputation of a product as well as its identity. On the EU level, trademarks are administered by the European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO) (formerly known as OHIM—the EU’s office for the harmonization of the internal market). The benefit of using trademarks as an innovation indicator is that it captures small firms and covers both the manufacturing and service industries.

Nevertheless, companies (e.g. from the creative industries) are often unaware of the opportunities of trademark protection and consequently do not register trademarks despite being innovative (Castaldi 2018). In addition, the product classes of trademarks are far more aggregated than the fine-grained patent classification, limiting their usefulness. Furthermore, innovations generated by universities and public research organisations are – again in contrast to patents – in general also not covered because of their missing commercial interest (Mendonça 2004). Therefore, the interest of innovation researchers, but also policymakers in this new data source is still quite limited in comparison to the long lasting and broad usage of patents as patent indicators. Nevertheless,

trademarks are often used as a complementary measure to patents, e.g. in the European Innovation Scoreboard.

4.1.5 Design Rights

Within the service sector, the creative industries have attracted the attention of policymakers in the last decade due to their increasing economic relevance. Design rights reflect areas of innovation, such as creativity and new ideas as well as certain industries and sectors, that are not well captured by patents. Thus they provide an innovation indicator complementary to patents and trademarks (Filitz et al. 2015). A notorious example of when design made headlines was when starting in 2011; Apple filed lawsuits against Samsung on the grounds that they deemed them to be copying the designs of their iPhones and iPads. These examples highlight that legal conflicts regarding Intellectual Property Rights are not only connected to patents and trademarks but also design rights.

Filitz et al. (2015) provide an overview of the literature on design protection as well as Registered Community Designs (EU level) which is one of the ways in which proprietors can register their designs. The authors outline how little has been researched on design innovation and protection and outline the possibilities in terms of design protection as innovation indicators. Looking at CIS data, it was found that firms that innovate use more design rights than those who do not (Livesey and Moultrie 2008). Furthermore, that design protection is the only more widely used 'Appropriability mechanism' in low-tech industries than in high-tech ones (Mairesse and Mohnen 2004).

Indeed, registered design might be a more appropriate in analysing innovation in more traditional industries and provide complementarity to patents which often are too heavily centred in technological innovation. Registered Community Designs (RCD), which are also processed by EUIPO, provide ample opportunities to analyse design protection throughout the EU. The number of design applications doubled from 40,000 in 2003 to 80,000 in 2011. Key to understanding RCD is the notion that they are not only cheap compared to trademarks and patents but have far less stringent requirements and are only deemed invalid when challenged (Filitz et al. 2015). In terms of RCDs as innovation indicators, they do have the benefit of reflecting additional innovative activities in low-tech industries with a large amount of centralised data from a wide array of countries. However, problems arise that designs have lower acceptance barriers, i.e. registration is sufficient without an ex-ante examination, and unlike with patents there is no way of ascertaining the value of design, e.g. via citations. Furthermore, design filings depend on industry, companies' strategies and awareness (probably similar to trademark usage, see Castaldi 2018) as well as legal and country-specific contexts. Therefore, their representativeness related to innovation is certainly more limited compared to patents, which is also reflected by the very small number of scientific studies making use of design registrations as indicators.

4.1.6 Composite Indicators

With the development of innovation research as a discipline, consensus was reached that the measurement of science and technology requires indicators

along many dimensions because no ideal variable for science or innovation has been developed. In detail, Gault (2010) postulates that single indicators do not tell the whole story, need further indicators to be qualified (e.g. like company size), or have to be combined with additional information (e.g. an innovation new to a regional market is quite different to an innovation new to the global market).

Therefore, in many cases, multiple indicators have been developed and used. However, the recognition of the need to measure multiple dimensions of science, technology and innovation and the weaknesses associated with focusing simply on one of the indicators outlined above has led to the development of composite indicators to enlighten policymakers responsible for science, technology and innovation.

According to the OECD, a composite indicator refers to the compiling of individual indicators underlined by a particular theory and model of a multi-dimensional subject (e.g. competitiveness) (OECD Glossary). An example of composite indicators is the 'European Union Scoreboard (EIS)'. Though they are used in a range of contexts, composite indicators are also associated with the practices of 'Benchmarking' and 'Scoreboarding' (Grupp and Moguee 2004). The former refers to comparing oneself to the strongest competitor or the most successful in a sector in order to identify best practises and ways to optimise performance. The latter is similar to sports scoreboards in terms of comparing progress, certain comparable points and so forth between companies. They are, for example, used to measure productivity.

Composite indicators are seen as beneficial for multiple reasons. They can shed light on complex multi-faceted problems, can help shed light on a country's performance and efficiency, and can be used in the setting of priorities. However, they also suffer from several strong criticisms (which are often also applicable to scoreboarding and benchmarking). Composite indicators can be misleading (not robust in light of sensitivity analysis), might risk oversimplification, involve subjective choices with a theoretical foundation, might disguise certain failures as well as not encapsulating other valuable dimensions, and can be subject to manipulation and biases (Archibugi et al. 2009, Grupp and Moguee 2004, Grupp & Schubert 2010, Kozłowski 2015, OECD Workshop on Composite Indicators). Despite these weaknesses, policymakers and other stakeholders still rely on composite indicators for managing or at least justifying their innovation policy at the macro level.

4.2 Further Problems with Traditional Indicators

The culmination of indicators assembled can help shed light on developments that are hard to quantify directly. However, indicators are also limited in their capacity to depict the innovative environment in a timely fashion, often suffering from a rear-view perspective. They inherently depict only a slice of what occurs in reality and as such according to Hardeman and Vertesy (2016, p. 169): "Indicators are not a given; rather, they are actively constructed." Additional issues arise regarding the use of innovation indicators when these become a goal unto themselves within the framework of

Goodhart's law. This refers to the notion that "once STI indicators are made targets for STI policy, such indicators lose most of the information content that qualify them to play such a role" (Freeman and Soete 2009, p. 583).

In particular, Iizuka and Hollanders (2016) outline various problematic aspects related to innovation indicators:

1. Misinterpretation of innovation indicator

Assuming linear progression of innovation that R&D precedes innovation

Assuming that more/higher performance on an indicator is always better (Foray and Hollanders, 2015);

Assuming that more innovation automatically leads to development (Soete, 2013).

2. Inappropriate use of innovation indicator

Compare indicators, which are not comparable (due to different collection methods, assumptions, measurements, industrial structure);

Applying same indicator criteria in different sector and country setting without careful consideration of characteristics or new contexts in which the indicators are being applied.

3. Misuse of innovation indicator for policy purposes

Blindly applying the R&D/GDP target (in developing countries, it is 1% and in developed countries, it is 3%) as a policy goal without understanding a country's industrial structure and HR composition;

Applying the indicator to policy formulation without understanding the underlying conceptual design and data collection procedure;

Ignoring the country/sector/industrial structural context when interpreting the innovation indicators for policy purposes;

Relying only on composite indicator ranking to monitor, evaluate and formulate innovation policy (and to make political statements that would mislead the public).

4. Overlooked issues of innovation indicators in policy domain

Omitting important sources of innovation which are actually vital for the economy and therefore for policy formulation (in developed context, e.g. vocational education as an alternative to tertiary education (Foray and Hollanders, 2015) Globalization of business activities in developed context (Edquist and Zabala-Iturriagoitia, 2015), Non R&D oriented innovation (i.e user led innovation/household innovation, public sector innovation?), in developing countries, informal R&D (user led innovation/household innovation), those who are trying to innovate from those who do not do anything, External sources of knowledge (Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), exports, GVC), informal sector, other productive sectors important in developing countries).

Ignoring the dynamic nature of industrial structure and relevance of selected indicators.

5. Mismatch of needs between user and producers of innovation indicator

a. Ignoring the results of innovation survey for policy elaboration (because the data come late (questions about its usefulness))

b. Ignoring the importance of comparability for the indicators (changing questions not to add).

Source: Iizuka and Hollanders (2016, p. 129)

One of the most significant depictions of problems associated with current indicators and innovation analyses (with subsequent policy implications) is the case of the Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) or Standard Occupational Classification (SOC) codes (Bakhshi and Mateos-Garcia 2016). These are used to classify industrial sectors and job areas. However, they are only updated at long intervals, e.g. only every ten years for SIC codes, which is problematic considering the dynamic innovative environment, where a new technology or innovation might arise and be so

dramatic that they do not fit within the traditional classification. Indeed, a completely new segment requiring its own classification might emerge. This is problematic because identifying whether a certain new innovative area is benefiting from certain inputs, investments and policy is hard to ascertain, as that particular area cannot be identified separately. Yet again, it is not that indicators are necessarily poor at measuring innovation, but rather they are limited in doing so. Indeed, the traditional tools and indicators should not necessarily be wholly replaced but rather, complemented. This leads to the crux of the issue, namely that policymakers need "...access to timely, high quality, and relevant data in order to identify pressing policy concerns, inform program design and policy choice, conduct forecasts, monitor policy implementation and evaluate impact" (Results for America 2017, p. 13). Hence, traditional tools are complemented by modern developments including the use of 'Big Data' and 'Machine Learning'. Before considering new ways of gathering information and indicators to map the innovation landscape, however, we must first identify what kind of evidence innovation policymakers require.

Still et al. (2011) present a paradigm shift in innovation indicators starting from the change of the traditional closed innovation paradigm driven by companies and focused on technology, which could be measured by traditional indicators, like patents, to open innovation including many more stakeholders, e.g. users. This shift is accompanied by a change in the data sources mainly relying on surveys and registers, like those provided by patent offices in the past to digital footprints of innovation actors of the present and future. Furthermore, the original lack of structured data is substituted by an information overload of mainly unstructured, but also incomplete and therefore biased, data. Finally, the significantly time-delayed available and often manually processed innovation indicators are complemented by real-time and computer-powered processed innovation indicators. The new technological options allow individual interactive and visualised treatment of the data, but also now- and place-casting of innovation activities (Guzman and Stern 2017) eventually getting down to the IS level.

	Analog	Digital
Innovation	Companies R&D, closed innovation Few innovation actors New technology <i>Tangibles</i> Waterfall-model of innovation Patents, scientific publications, number of new products	Network of companies, (eco)systems Open innovation, co-creation Many innovation actors, including users New technology, new services, new processes, new products <i>Intangibles</i> Agile innovation, lean start-ups Time-to-market, scalability
Data	Surveys, company reporting Lack of data Structured data Statistically representative samples	Digital footprints of innovation actors Information overload Unstructured, unorganized, incomplete data Biased data
Indicators	Lagging behind Manual processes Table format, some graphs	Possibilities for real-time Economical computer-powered processes, though challenging Interactive, data-driven visualizations, network visualizations, timelines, geospatial representations, (eco)systemic level

Table 4: Paradigm shift in innovation indicators (Source: Still et al. 2011)

5. Relation between Innovation Policy and Measurement of Innovation

5.1 Evidence Needs of Policy Makers

According to Shaxson (2005), policymaking needs evidence for a variety of reasons. First, policymakers have to understand the policy environment and its changes. Second, the possible effects of policy changes have to be assessed in order to choose the options with the preferred outcomes. In this context, evidence can show the links between policy objectives and actual policy initiatives in general and specify the concrete measures needed to achieve specific goals. Evidence is also needed to convince other stakeholders to support policy goals and in the implementation of policies. Finally, evidence increases transparency in government processes. These general needs can be extrapolated to innovation policy.

In terms of the specific evidence required for innovation policymakers, the most notable evidence gained is that from answering the questions of what the ‘social returns on public and private expenditures on Science Technology and Innovation (STI)’ and the impact of STI on ‘Economic Growth, Competitiveness and Jobs’ (Litan et al. 2014). Policymakers would like to know where to invest to best support an innovative environment (Grupp and Schubert 2010). Indicators and quantitative measures are useful and highlight certain trends. Other questions include: where the innovative hotspots are situated, how the role of minorities could be increased, what kind of collaborative relationships are required, and whether there has been a cross-

fertilization from other disciplines. Nonetheless, other factors are also of interest such as protecting intellectual property rights, profits and limiting systemic risks. Overall, “[a]ll of these top-level issues – drivers, trends, advances, vulnerabilities, relationships, and distributions – have underlying metrics that users want” (Litan et al. 2014, p. 30). Furthermore, Table 5 outlines what type of evidence is required to ascertain the effectiveness of the state’s governance of innovative activity. Table 6 provides a list of specific innovation-related policy questions.

Key Questions Social Returns on Public and Private Expenditures on STI Impact on Economic Growth, Competitiveness, and Jobs			
STI Indicators Drivers, Trends, Advances, Vulnerabilities, Culture/Climate, and Distributions			
Actors	Activities	Linkages	Outcomes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individuals • Collectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Teams – Governments – Education and research institutions – Businesses – Private nonprofit organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Invention • Development • Engineering/design • Innovation • Diffusion • Education • Training • Capital investment • Job mobility • Firm dynamics • Policy, regulation & governance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grants • Contracts • Collaboration • Partnerships • Codevelopment • Copublication • Social networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge stocks • Social capital • Intangibles • Products and services • Productivity • Product life cycles • Trade in S&T products • Trade in R&D services • Job mobility • Firm dynamics • Socioeconomic impacts/well-being

Table 5: A policy-driven framework for STI indicators (Source: Litan et al. 2014)

Innovation-Related Policy Questions
What kinds of innovations create jobs and what kinds of jobs?
What specific innovations have made the most important contributions to economic growth and over what time period?
Where should the government spend its R&D dollars?
Can government procurement policy be changed to encourage innovation?
What new industries, occupations, and skill sets are being created by recent innovations, and are current educational institutions equipping enough people with the skills needed to take maximum advantage of these changes?
How important is formal R&D to the innovative process, as opposed to organizational changes and continued on-the-job tinkering by employees and their managers?
Does the globalization of R&D increase or decrease the ability to turn research into marketed innovations? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are U.S. firms conducting more or less of their research activities offshore and does it even matter where this activity takes place? • Is the United States innovating more or less than other countries?
Are small companies more likely to innovate than big companies?
In which types of firms—small or large, young or mature—do the most important innovations occur, and is this pattern stable?
How do service firms innovate and create new knowledge?
What are the sources of funding for innovation activities, including R&D?
Are potential innovations not reaching market because of too much regulation, taxes that are too high, or too much market power in product markets?

Are potential innovations being stalled because of insufficient funding, not enough skilled workers, or too many obstacles to skilled immigrants?
Are innovations not being brought to market or implemented because of misguided patent policies?

Table 6: Innovation-related policy questions (Source: Litan et al. 2014)

However, as with indicators and scoreboards, attempts to measure the performance of policy measures suffer from similar strong limitations. These include the possibility of being influenced by the expectations of governments as well as being highly contextual where at best one might gain a limited amount of information about possible future trajectories or at worst misleading ones (Feller 2013). In addition, Feller (2013) highlights that the link between the measurement of innovation performance and decision making in innovation policy can vary significantly. On the one hand, the results of performance measures can result in admonitions or encouragement to improve in the future without accompanying positive incentives or negative sanctions to trigger changes in policymaking and implementation. On the other hand, they may induce or mandate significant changes at the innovation policy or programme level, but also on the organizational level, e.g. research organizations or universities. For example, the innovation performance in previous periods will influence the budgets available for the future.

In addition to the variance in the role of evidence, i.e. innovation indicators, for innovation policy, Hill (2013) addresses the general direction between evidence and innovation policy. He argues that on the one hand the needs of policymakers shape the demands for innovation indicators, but on the other hand the availability of innovation indicators tends to shape the demand for public policies. For example, policymakers ask for the assessment of the competitiveness of specific industries and are therefore interested in their innovativeness. Since information about R&D and patents is easily available, although as elaborated above not necessarily satisfactory to needs, policymakers are encouraged to consider policies to support additional R&D spending without knowing whether more R&D consistently leads to more innovation. Related to established indicators, Hill (2013) observes additional requirements for more detailed indicators, e.g. of greater granularity in geographical, sectoral or technological dimension covering future directions. Finally, he claims – without providing evidence – that the availability of new innovation data or indicators, i.e. new evidence, will create demand for policy innovations intending to influence these new indicators, even if their quality might be inferior.

5.2 The Role of Innovation Indicators in Innovation Policy

In general, innovation indicators are used for improving innovation policy design by providing information on the need to initiate a new policy or about progress of implemented policies made by comparing the current status with the past. In addition, the comparison can also be made with other countries or regions to identify the need to start innovation policy initiatives to avoid lagging behind the others.

In addition to regulation, economic and soft instruments as types of innovation policies mentioned above in section 3, Borrás (2008) introduces a fourth type of policy instrument, the meta-instruments. They are not intended to modify situations in the society and economy as the three above mentioned types of instruments but are designed and used with the purpose of providing intelligence to the process of

formulating innovation policy itself, i.e. to policy learning as the sixth condition of an effective governance of innovation policy (see Table 7). Borrás (2008) perceives innovation indicators, policy benchmarks and technology foresight as the three most prominent examples of meta-instruments related to innovation policy. The use of indicators to perform regulatory foresight exercises has recently emerged (Blind 2008) and has been further leveraged to identifying the future needs for standards in advance (Goluchowicz and Blind 2011).

In contrast to Borrás (2008), Gault (2010) distinguishes four ways innovation indicators are used for innovation policy purposes, i.e. monitoring, benchmarking, evaluating, and forecasting or foresighting. In detail, the international innovation system, the linkages within and between national, regional or technological systems of innovation can be monitored as well as the implementation of research, technology or innovation projects, but also specific quantitative indicators of the goals of innovation policies, such as the goal of the EU to invest 3% of GDP in R&D. Innovation indicators are also used for benchmarking between countries and regions, but also institutions and even individuals. Furthermore, the performance of research and innovation programmes, and Higher Education Institutes and Public Research Organisations, can be evaluated based on research and innovation indicators. In addition, the potential development of emerging sciences, technologies and industries can be assessed using innovation indicators. Finally, innovation indicators can provide a background to foresight processes, but are in general complemented by technology- or innovation-specific information. In addition to these four functions, Gault (2010) mentions that one can use indicators to make a case for further analysis leading to policy development elaborating the example of user innovation, which is clearly a relevant component of the overall innovation performance of a country. However, the treatment of their intellectual property rights challenges the existing regulatory frameworks and asks for the intervention of innovation policymakers.

Conditions for effective governance	Conditions for effective governance
A strategic innovation policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The existence of an explicit political vision and priority-setting • Evidence that the vision and priorities are transposed to the choice, design and implementation of innovation policy instruments
A positive administrative coordination of innovation policy at the middle level of executive departments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The existence of explicit and co-operative mechanisms of vertical and horizontal coordination • Evidence of clear patterns of actor's interactions explicitly conducive to reduce redundancies and enhance complementarity and synergy of governmental actions
A rapid adaptation of the formal institutional framework in the innovation system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence that the formal institutional framework is adapting rapidly • Evidence that recent adaptations in the formal institutional framework have been conducive to the desired levels and patterns of innovative performance
A balanced diversity creation and market selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The enforcement of the principle of additionality by prudent diversity creation. • Evidence that governmental action secures incentives for market selection process
A clear distribution of roles between public and private actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extended formalised contractual agreement between partners in complex and 'grey' zone of public-private partnerships • Evidence of conditionality of public involvement in these types of public-private interactions
Policy learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers' active development and use of meta-instruments • Policymakers' active participation in learning platforms
Public legitimacy and accountability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of well-endowed participatory frameworks in the innovation policymaking process complementing formal democratic channels • Evidence of political accountability in innovation-related matters

Table 7: Conditions for effective governance of innovation policy and their analytical criteria (Source: Borrás 2008)

5.3 Desired Attributes of Innovation Indicators

Shaxson (2005) outlines how evidence needs to be 'robust'. Robustness consists of 'Credibility', 'Generalisability', 'Reliability', 'Objectivity' and 'Rootedness'. In order for evidence to be credible, its rationale must be clear and coherent, and its analysis strong and rigorous. In terms of being generalised, the question arises whether evidence gathered for one issue can be used for another and to what extent. Whether evidence is reliable for policymaking is linked to its suitability as a solid foundation for future policy monitoring and evaluation. The objectivity of evidence always depends on the possible biases (e.g. ideological/theoretical) that may frame the collection of evidence. Rootedness refers partly to the context of the evidence, how were terms defined, who was included and whether all relevant stakeholders were considered. Moreover, rootedness is linked to looking at the evidence as a whole, including the process, ideas, ambiguities and assumptions behind this evidence.

Iizuka and Hollanders (2017) summarize the required attributes for innovation indicators mentioned in the literature. First, the quality of innovation indicators (see also Gault 2013) must be credible and analytically sound, i.e. they are carefully evaluated for their conceptual soundness and measurement errors should be minimized. Measurability and robustness are given, if stable and obtainable information with wider coverage of countries as well as time periods is available.

Furthermore, transparency of indicators is required, e.g. the collection methods of indicators. Second, indicators should be policy neutral, i.e. impartial to political motivations. In general, explicit numbers and statistical analyses do not allow subjective interpretation. However, political forces may influence the definition and the selection of data. They highlight that timeliness of data is crucial for indicators to be used in the policymaking process, whereas comparability is critical for monitoring, benchmarking and evaluation exercises. By reducing information about innovation into a concise form, indicators can contribute to the communicability of an innovation policy agenda to the general public. Third, accessibility of innovation indicators to users does not only refer to their availability but also user-friendliness. This also encompasses their affordability, because collecting innovation indicators can be costly. Finally, relevance to the goals of innovation policy is the most critical attribute for innovation indicators, taking into account that for different countries and regions different indicators are relevant.

To illustrate a set of requirements for innovation indicators in a specific innovation policy context, we list the following ten items presented by the European Commission (2010) as headline indicators for innovation in support of the Europe 2020 strategy:

1. Simple and understandable	An innovation indicator, which should be linked to a specific policy objective, has to be easily understandable for the audience, e.g. policy makers, but also industry representatives. It should have a precise technical meaning but should not be too technical that threatens its comprehensibility. The link to the targets should be so sharp, that it has the power to mobilize to call for action.
2. Sizable and direct	The indicator has to cover a significant share of the issue, e.g. innovation in services. It should be sizable and relevant to its substance, but also linked to the framework conditions of the relevant innovation system.
3. Objective	Indicators based on answers to survey questionnaires are important component for the in-depth analysis of innovation. However, they should be complemented by hard data, like patents, as much as possible.
4. Presently computable	In general, innovation indicators should be available quickly, be easily measurable and based on existing data. However, the formulation of a new innovation indicator could serve as a stimulus for the initial gathering and processing of the necessary data to produce it. One example is the expansion of the geographical coverage of existing innovation data, e.g. to developing countries.
5. Stable	Innovation indicators should be sufficiently recognized and tested that they can last for several years without modifications being needed. Furthermore, the indicators should keep the same meaning over the years, i.e. an increase in the value of the indicator should reflect progress in innovation rather than changing framework conditions, e.g. the expansion of patentability of inventions.
6. Internationally comparable	Innovation indicators should allow the calibration of the position of a specific country relative to other areas of the world, because this is an essential aim of an innovation policy benchmarking exercise. Therefore, innovation indicators should be available for other areas of the world.
7. Decomposable	Innovation indicators and possible targets should be translatable into specific targets for different countries or even regions. This adaptability of the indicators will be a key success factor, because innovation policy takes place at the country or even regional level. A related requirement is unbiasedness, i.e. the innovation indicators should not <i>a priori</i> be strongly correlated with characteristics of the innovation systems of specific countries and regions. These biases can be corrected for by using indicators weighted by GDP or expressing rates of change rather than levels.
8. Low susceptibility to manipulation	Innovation indicators should not be so focused or narrow in scope that behavioural changes of the units of measurement, e.g. companies or research institutes, can change their meaning or significance.
9. Easy to handle technically	Innovation indicators should allow a consistent measurement at different levels of aggregation.

<p>10. Sensitive to stakeholders' views</p>	<p>Innovation indicators need the support of the majority of the stakeholders, e.g. companies or research organisations. Therefore, indicators constructed for a supranational level have to be adapted to national or regional level in order to receive the endorsement of the stakeholders active at these levels.</p>
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Table 8: Required characteristics of innovation indicators (Source: based on European Commission 2010)

In summary, starting from the general requirements for evidence in the context of policymaking, we have presented the required attributes for innovation indicators followed by a specific set of items developed within a specific innovation policy initiative.

6. New Data for Innovation Policy

6.1 Overview

In light of the limitations of traditional datasets and indicators, as well as questions that innovation policymakers wish to have answered, new possibilities for policymaking are provided by recent technological developments and the rise of Big Data, advanced analytics, and new forms to communicate the findings. Indeed, with the proliferation of digital technologies throughout both public and private domains, unprecedented amounts of data and information are now available and provide the possibility of transforming evidence-based policymaking. However, Oliver et al. (2014) argue that the opportunities for evidence-based policymaking have failed to be fully exploited. They claim that failure to exploit evidence-based policymaking opportunities can be explained in part because of the little empirical analysis of the processes used to inform researchers or decision-makers. Consequently, they argue that better empirical descriptions and analysis of how research and policy interact are required.

Data typically used to develop R&I indicators can be broadly categorised into two different groups: “official data” curated and maintained by one or more organisations; and data in the form of “digital traces”, which often does not have an official entity generating, collecting and maintaining it, and exists as a result of activities other than the official development of R&I indicators. Official data includes public administrative data (e.g. patent and publications records) and official surveys such as the Community Innovation Survey. Official R&I data is usually consistent over time, controlled and well structured. Digital traces used to develop R&I indicators include unstructured data within websites, APIs developed for a range of purposes other than R&I indicators, data associated with new digital technologies such as mobile phones, social media and even tracking/GPS and sensors. Digital traces of this type are often highly distributed, generated and published at a faster rate than official data and are not accountable for data quality or consistency over time.

The process of linking official data and digital traces has increased, making new sources useful complements to more traditional datasets. With larger amounts of data being gathered and provided, there is an increase in opportunity for data to inform all segments of the policy cycle.

Various research outlines how digital technologies and big data can capture relevant information and possibly forecast trends at a much faster pace than ‘traditional’ datasets. For instance, in 2008 Google initiated the Google Flu Trends project: using search queries in their search engines, they could predict areas where the flu was occurring quicker than the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Lazer et al. (2014) criticise the methodology of the Google Flu project in terms of policymaking, outlining how it cannot be replicated by all. With Wikipedia, this criticism does not apply with their monitoring of global diseases as the data is freely available and thus replicable (Generous et al. 2014). Limitations do exist, however, as those searching about a global disease are not those that are most affected by it, i.e. those with limited internet connection. The beauty with digital technologies however, is that there is always an alternative path, where for example, Bengtsson (2011) analysed the spread of disease in Haiti after an earthquake using mobile phone data and geolocations and then compared it with official statistics to check the validity (mobile data was found to be more accurate). Social media is also an alternative outlet for

gathering information for policymaking. Trends in social media as well as concerns mentioned can be measured without requiring surveys and thus are more timely as well as less costly. Table 9 provides an overview of the new possibilities in collecting, processing and analysing/visualising data:

Function	Examples
Data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web crawling and scraping software; • Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to access data automatically from websites and online databases.
Data storage and processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database technologies, including 'non-relational' databases to store non-tabular data efficiently, • Cloud services for remote storage and parallel processing of data; • 'Big data' framework to distribute data jobs across many machines, and speed up analysis.
Data analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software applications for data analysis; supervised and unsupervised machine learning methods for classification, prediction and clustering, natural language processing and social network analysis.
Data reporting and visualisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools and products for interactive data visualisation, reports, dashboards and data-driven websites.

Table 9: Summary of data technologies, tools and methods (Source: Bakhshi and Mateos-Garcia 2016)

6.2 Data Sources

Poel et al. (2015) reviewed fifty-eight policy initiatives in a multitude of policy areas and outline the data sources that are used. Most projects use administrative data and information provided by statistical offices. However, sensor-based data as a new type of data source is already increasingly used than large survey data.

Figure 6: Types of data sources for policymaking (Source: Poel et al. 2015)

Horton and Tambe (2015) look at the relationship between big data and labour economics and find a multitude of new avenues in finding rich data and information that are also applicable to the field of innovation. Employment websites such as LinkedIn and Monster provide a wealth of information regarding applicant skills, work and education histories, geographical location as well as on what jobs are being searched for as well as offered. Online labour markets (e.g. Uber, TaskRabbit) provide a unique amount of information. Collaboration platforms such as GitHub or Slack outline in detail the individual skills, contributions, project and people management that are used in the production of software. Knowledge sharing platforms such as Quora provide insights into the technical concerns employees might have, how they tackle them and thus gain knowledge. Social media platforms provide a broad spectrum of information, from tastes, interests, hobbies, to frequented locations and events, social demographics and even at times career goals.

6.3 Data Analytics and Visualisation

A variety of techniques exist to collect and exploit the value of Big Data. How this information is analysed and presented however, often depends on what form and type of data are collected (e.g. administrative data or social media data). This again influences what analytical tools one uses. Data analytics can range from simple statistical programs such as Excel to complex high-end computing software and approaches themselves also differ widely. However, as illustrated in Figure 7, the majority of analyses are descriptive. More advanced methods, like predictive analytics and sentiment mining, are used in a minority of the projects.

Visualisation tools are often centred around geographical location. This can range from depicting spending patterns based on time or demographics, commuting patterns (e.g. Guardians Interactive maps) to outlining innovative hubs in cities. They are often used to depict complex information or data in a more tangible and accessible manner whether it be for informing citizens or indeed, policymakers.

Figure 7: Types of data analysis (Source: Poel et al. 2015)

6.4 New Data used along the Policy Cycle

There have been attempts in academia to use new data and/or analytical methodologies to inform policymaking process and policy cycle. In line with the traditional Triple Helix innovation model (university-industry-government relations), where the importance of universities for innovation is emphasised, findings from academia will be considered for innovation policy. Furthermore, due consideration is given to the Quadruple Helix (conceptualized within a knowledge society/economy) (Bonaccorsi et al. 2016) and subsequent Quintuple Helix model namely, the entwined connection between economy and society and that innovation should emerge within a sustainable environment (Carayannis et al. 2012).

Boyack et al. (2002) created a data mining platform that visualised the science and technology areas of a company using bibliographic information to identify a company's central technology and its development over time. This methodology could aid governments throughout the policy cycle in ascertaining the viability of investments in

R&D and innovation. With a similar aim, Porter (2005) used another data mining software (Vantage Point) “...integrating the steps of data cleaning, statistical analyses, trend analyses and information visualisation” (Campbell et al. 2017, p. 15). Bakshi et al. (2015) looked at the impact of a technology conference on participant networks by looking at Twitter data, and Mateos-Garcia (2015) used data from the social platform Meetup to analyse the process by which technology networks are created (see Campbell et al. 2017 for an overview). With access to not only a far larger volume of data but also data on activities previously not captured, policymakers can utilise various analytical processes and tools to find answers to many more questions. Data can be gathered for every step of the policy cycle (see Figure 8). So far, data is expected to mainly be used for science and technology foresight and agenda setting, which was also the case decades ago (Blind et al. 1999). The use of the new data sources will certainly help the monitoring efforts of running innovation policy measures. The larger array of data inputs will also help to provide more robust indicators (Rafols et al. 2012).

However, the expected low usage of data in the evaluation phase of the policy life cycle might also go back to the findings by Teirlinck et al. (2013), indicating that the limited uptake of evaluation findings relates mainly to the lack of early and systematic involvement of a broad spectrum of stakeholders and the use of non-harmonised indicators and non-transferable evaluation methods. Similarly, Donovan (2011) argues that limited consultation between policymakers and the research evaluation community has led to a lack of policy-learning.

Figure 8: Expected use of data in policy cycle (Source: Poel et al. 2015)

6.5 Critiques of big and new data for innovation policy

Despite access to an unprecedented wealth of information as a result of big data as well as an exponential increase in the availability of analytical mechanisms to use these data, important critiques have emerged.

Firstly, though it might be assumed that the more information there is, the better it is especially within the context of evidence-based policymaking, is this necessarily the case? To be more precise, within the policy life cycle and considering that one cannot have fully complete information and that the full effects of a policy can often only be observed over a span of several years, does micro-managing within each step of the cycle make sense or work? More importantly, as innovation needs to be allowed to emerge organically, could it also not have adverse negative consequences? Furthermore, with consideration to natural cognitive limitations such as information overload, bounded rationality and biases, would such an increase in information have further negative consequences?

The notion of data visualisation is a good starting point in tackling such cognitive limitations. However, data visualisation might suffer from oversimplification and over-represent some factors whilst under-representing or even not accounting for others. This is particularly dangerous if the data upon which the visuals are based are too complex for policymakers to analyse themselves. Moreover, though progress has been made on the development of data analytical techniques with the use of big data, these are usually specific case studies and are highly contextual. Hence, there is very little space for a generalisable methodology, structure or theory and therefore of only limited applicability to policymakers.

Secondly, connected to the notion of cognitive biases is that policymaking is not a politically and ideologically neutral process where many policies are constructed and enacted for political purposes. Hence, an increase in information would often only have a limited impact but conversely, an increase in complex data would provide more opportunities of misuse and misinterpretation depending on the stakeholder's interest.

Thirdly, the use of Big Data and various analytical techniques raise privacy and ethical concerns. Indeed, a large amount of data is gathered, and the most useful ones are often sensitive (e.g. health-related data) not to mention some are protected by law where particular attention needs to be paid to the newly enacted General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Furthermore, as it is not clear whether having access to larger volumes of data and analysing them will necessarily result in better policies, the legitimisation of their use is further compromised.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, the literature review of innovation policy has revealed various insights relevant for the scoping phase of the project.

First, the literature about the role of indicators in evidence-based policy making is quite limited and it is only recently that some papers by political scientists are addressing the topic. In addition, the role of indicators for policymaking has been mainly discussed in the context of climate and health policies, but not for innovation policy, a finding that has been validated by scholars we approached working on innovation indicators and policy.

Second, indicators play different roles in the various phases of the policy life cycle. It is important to note that the common development of indicators is an important step in policy formulation and reduces the risk of developing indicators that will not be used or will have limited influence. These lessons must be taken into account in development of the further phases of EURITO.

Third, the development of innovation policy from market to system failure, and most recently mission orientation, will generate new demand for innovation indicators, because current indicators are not satisfying.

Fourth, the above-mentioned shift in justifying innovation policy requires also expanding the focus of innovation policy instruments from the supply to the demand side. This will generate additional demand for innovation indicators measuring impacts at the demand-side to be used both for ex-ante and ex-post assessments of demand-side oriented innovation policy instruments.

Fifth, there are many opportunities and threats for failure, from the very beginning of innovation indicator development to the use of innovation indicators and their impacts along the innovation policy cycle. These threats must be taken into account in the further phases of EURITO.

Sixth, the innovation indicators to be developed during EURITO have to fulfil several requirements, among them the RITO criteria, in order to gain acceptance among innovation policy makers. However, there are still threats of misuse and misinterpretation, which should be considered when scaling up and implementing the pilot innovation indicators proposed by EURITO.

Seventh, the previously mentioned challenges are valid both for existing traditional innovation indicators, but also for new indicators based on new large-scale databases. A few years ago, there was a shift in the paradigm of innovation indicators, from analog to digital, but this has still not been accomplished and can be further pushed by EURITO. However, this needs to take into account the above-mentioned requirements for developing and implementing influential innovation indicators that are actually used.

Finally, so far, we assumed that innovation policy is driving the development of innovation indicators. Yet, we have also been made aware of new innovation indicators driving innovation policy. Furthermore, the results of measuring innovation after a policy intervention can mean an obligatory commitment for readjusting

interventions. However, this could also be completely ignored by innovation policymakers and their administrations. EURITO aims to develop indicators not only fulfilling the RITO criteria in the narrow sense, but also indicators that are valued by policymakers in general.

References

- Archibugi D., Denni M., Filippetti A., (2009), 'The technological capabilities of nations: The state of the art of synthetic indicators', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 76, 917-931.
- Arundel A. and Hollanders, H. (2005) 'Policy, Indicators and Targets: Measuring the impacts of Innovation policies', *European Trend Chart on Innovation*, European Commission: enterprise Directorate-General
- Bakhshi, H., Davies, J., & Mateos-Garcia, J. (2015). The net effect: Using social media data to understand the impact of a conference on social networks. Online at: <https://www.nesta.org.uk/publications/net-effect-using-social-media-data-understand-impact-conference-social-networks>
- Bakhshi H., Mateos-Garcia J., (2016), 'New Data for Innovation Policy', NESTA Online at: <https://www.oecd.org/sti/106%20-%20Bakhshi%20and%20Mateos-Garcia%202016%20-%20New%20Data%20for%20Innovation%20Policy.pdf>
- Blind, K. (2008), 'Regulatory foresight: Methodologies and selected applications', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 75, 496-516.
- Blind, K., Edler, J., Frietsch, R., & Schmoch, U. (2006). Motives to patent: Empirical evidence from Germany', *Research Policy*, 35(5), 655-672.
- Blind, K., Cuhls, K., Grupp, H. (1999), 'Current Foresight Activities in Europe' *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 60 (1), 15-35.
- Blind, K., Cremers, K., Müller, E. (2009), 'The influence of strategic patenting on companies' patent portfolios', *Research Policy* 38 (2), 428-436.
- Boavida N., Moniz a., Laranja M., (2016), 'The process of construction of evidence: An analysis of the use of indicators in two decisions of innovation policy', 21st International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators (STI), Valencia, Spain, September 14-16, 2016
- Bonaccorsi, A., Catalano, G., Daraio, C., Moed H., (2016), 'Towards an Open Quadruple Helix Indicators Factory' Online at: https://www.oecd.org/sti/138%20-%20Bonaccorsi_Catalano_Daraio_Moed_OECD_BlueSky%20Conf_2016%20_25%20July%20final.pdf
- Borrás S., (2008), 'The Widening and Deepening of Innovation Policy: What Conditions Provide for Effective Governance?', PRIME International Conference, Europe-Latin America Conference on Science and Innovation Policy, Mexico City
- Borrás, S. and Edquist C., (2013), 'The choice of innovation policy instruments', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 80, 1513-1522.
- Borrás, S. and Edquist C., (2016), 'Conceptual Underpinning for Innovation Policy Design-Indicators and Instruments in Context, Paper prepared for OECD Blue Sky Conference III
- Boyack, K. , Wylie, B., & Davidson, G. (2002), 'Domain visualization using VxInsight for science and technology management' *JASIST*, 53(9), 764-774.

Butler, L. (2004), What happens when funding is linked to publication counts? In: Moed, H.F.; Glänzel, W; Schmoch, U. (Eds.), Handbook of Quantitative Science and Technology, Kluwer Academic Publishers, 389-340.

Campbell, D., Tippett C., Struck B., Lefebvre C., Côté G., Lalonde, B., Ventimiglia A., Roberge G., Archambault E. (2017), 'Data Mining: Knowledge and technology flows in priority domains within the private sector and between the public and private sectors, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (EC)

Carayannis E., Barth T., Campbell D., (2012), 'The Quintuple Helix innovation model: global warming as a challenge and driver for innovation', Innovation and Entrepreneurship 1, 1-12.

Castaldi. C. (2018), 'To trademark or not to trademark: The case of the creative and cultural industries', Research Policy, 47(3), 606-661.

Chaminade, C., Edquist, C. (2010). Rationales for public policy intervention in the innovation process: A systems of innovation approach. In Kuhlman, S., Shapira, P., Smits, R. (Eds.), Innovation policy – theory and practice. An international Handbook. London, UK: Edward Elgar Publishers.

Cohen, W. M., Nelson, R. R., & Walsh, J. P. (2000). Protecting their intellectual assets: Appropriability conditions and why US manufacturing firms patent (or not). NBER working paper series: Vol. 7552. Cambridge, Mass.: National Bureau of Economic Research. Retrieved from http://libero/Bibliothek/virtuell/2006/V2006_109916.pdf

Dodgson M., Hughes A., Foster J., Metcalfe S. (2011), 'Systems thinking, market failure, and the development of innovation policy: The case of Australia, Research Policy, Vol. 40, issue 9, 1145-1156.

Donovan, C. (2011), 'State of the art in assessing research impact: introduction to a special issue', Research Evaluation, 20(3), 175–179.

Edler, J., Fagerberg, J. (2017), 'Innovation policy: what, why, and how', Oxford Review of Economic Policy, Vol. 33 No. 1, 2-23.

Edquist C. (2011), 'Design of innovation policy through diagnostic analysis: identification of systemic problems (or failures)', Industrial and Corporate Change, Vol. 20 No. 6, 1725-1753.

European Commission (2010), 'Elements for the setting-up of headline indicators for innovation in support of the Europe 2020 strategy: Report of the High Level Panel on the Measurement of Innovation', Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Brussels, <https://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/pdf/elements-for-the-setting-up-of-headline-indicators2013.pdf>

European Commission (2013), 'Innovation Union: A pocket guide on a Europe 2020 initiative' Online at: <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6f270d5f-8086-4b70-82b2-c4353d253720/language-en>

European Commission (2018), 'Science, Research and Innovation Performance of the EU 2018: Strengthening the foundations for Europe's future', Brussels,

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/rec-17-015-srip-report2018_mep-web-20180228.pdf

Feller I., (2013), 'Performance measures as forms of evidence for science and technology policy decisions', *Journal of Technology Transfer* 38, 565-576.

Freeman, C. (1982) Technological infrastructure and international competitiveness. Draft paper submitted to the OECD Ad Hoc Group on Science, Technology and Competitiveness, August 1982 (mimeo).

Freeman, C. (1987) *Technology Policy and Economic Performance: Lessons from Japan* (London: Pinter).

Freeman C. and Soete L. (2009), 'Developing science, technology and innovation indicators: What we can learn from the past', *Research Policy* 38, 583-589.

Filitz R., Henkel J., Tether B. (2015) 'Protecting aesthetic innovations? An exploration of the use of registered community designs', *Research Policy* 44, 1192-1206.

Gault F. and Von Hippel E. (2009), 'The prevalence of user innovation and free innovation transfers: implications for statistical indicators and innovation policy', MIT Sloan School of Management Working paper #4722-09

Gault F. (2010), *Innovation Strategies for a Global Economy, Development, Implementation, Measurement and Management*. Edward Elgar and IDRC, Cheltenham, UK and Northampton, MA USA and Ottawa.

Gault F. (2011), 'Social impacts of the development of science, technology and innovation indicators', UNU-Merit Working papers

Gault F. (2018), 'Defining and measuring innovation in all sectors of the economy', *Research Policy* 47, 617-622.

Generous, N.; Fairchild, G., Deshpande, A., Del Valle, S. Y., Priedhorsky, R. (2014) Global Disease Monitoring and Forecasting with Wikipedia, *PLOS* November 13, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003892>

Goluchowicz K., Blind K. (2011), 'Identification of future fields of standardisation: An explorative application of the Delphi methodology', *Technological Forecasting & Social Change* 78, 1526-1541.

Grupp H. (1998), *Foundation of the Economics of Innovation: Theory, Measurement and Practice*, Edward Elgar, Cheltenham UK.

Grupp H., Moguee M.E., (2004), 'Indicators for national science and technology policy: how robust are composite indicators', *Research Policy*, Vol. 33, issue 9, 1373-1384.

Grupp H., Schubert T., (2010), 'Review and new evidence on composite innovation indicators for evaluating national performance', *Research Policy* 39, 67-78.

Guzman J., Stern S., (2017), 'Nowcasting and Placecasting Entrepreneurial Quality and Performance', in: *Measuring Entrepreneurial Businesses: Current Knowledge and Challenges* edited by John Haltiwanger, Erik Hurst, Javier Miranda, and Antoinette Schoar, National Bureau of Economic Research Studies in Income and Wealth

Hardeman S., Vertesy D., (2016), 'Evidence-based policy learning: the case of the research excellence indicator', 21st International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators (STI), Valencia, Spain, September 14-16, 2016

Harhoff D., Narin F., Scherer F.M., Vopel K. (1999), 'Citation frequency and the value of patented inventions', *Review of Economics and Statistics* 81 (3), 511-515.

Hekkert M., Suurs R., Negro S., Kuhlmann S., Smits R., (2007), 'Functions of innovation systems: A new approach for analysing technological change', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Vol. 74, issue 4, 413-432.

Hill C. T. (2013): US innovation strategy and policy: an indicator perspective, in: *Handbook of Innovation Indicators and Measurement* edited by F. Gault, Edward Elgar Publishing Limited, Cheltenham, 333-346.

Horton J., and Tambe P., (2015), 'Labor Economists Get Their Microscope: Big Data and Labor Market Analysis', Online at: http://john-joseph-horton.com/papers/labor_econ_microscope.pdf

Iizuka M., Hollanders H., (2016), 'Innovation indicators: Towards a User's guide', 21st International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators (STI), Valencia, Spain, September 14-16, 2016

Iizuka M., Hollanders H., (2016), 'The need to customize innovation indicators in developing countries', *UNU-MERIT Working Papers #2017-032*,

Janger J., Schubert T., Andries, P., Rammer, C., Hoskens M., (2017) 'The EU 2020 innovation indicator: A step forward in measuring innovation outputs and outcomes?', *Research Policy* 46, 30-42.

Kleinknecht A., Van Montfort K., Brouwer E. (2002), 'The non-trivial choice between innovation indicators', *Econ. Innov. New Techn.*, Vol. 11, No. 2, 109-121.

Kozłowski J., (2015), 'Innovation indices: the need for positioning them where they properly belong', *Scientometrics* 104, 609-628.

Lehtonen, M., (2015), 'Indicators: tools for informing, monitoring or controlling?', in: *The Tools of Policy Formulation: Actors, Capacities, Venues and Effects*. New Horizons in Public Policy edited by Andrew J. Jordan and John R Turnpenny, Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, UK and Northampton, MA, USA, 76-99.

Lehtonen, M., (2017), 'Operationalizing information: measures and indicators in policy formulation', in: *Handbook of Policy Formulation* edited by Michael Howlett and Ishani Mukherjee, Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, 261-281.

Litan R.E., Wyckoff A.W., Fealing K. H., (2014), 'Capturing Change in Science, Technology and Innovation: Improving Indicators to Inform Policy', The National Academies Press, Washington D.C. (USA)

Livesey, F., Moultrie, J., (2008) 'Do trademarks and design registrations provide a better perspective on national innovation activity?' In: *DIME Conference on the Creative Industries and Intellectual Property*, London.

Lundvall, B.. (1985) Product Innovation and User–Producer Interaction (Aalborg: Aalborg University Press).

Lundvall, B (2007), ‘National Innovation Systems- Analytical Concept and Development Tool’, Industry and Innovation, Vol. 14, Issue 1, 95-119.

Mairesse, J., Mohnen, P., (2004) ‘Intellectual property in services: what do we learn from innovation surveys?’ In: OECD (Ed.), Patents, Innovation and Economic Performance. OECD, Paris, 227–245.

Mateos-Garcia, J. (2015). Using meetup data to explore the UK digital tech landscape. Online at: <http://www.nesta.org.uk/blog/using-meetup-data-explore-uk-digital-tech-landscape>

Martin B., (2016), ‘Twenty challenges for innovation studies’, Science and Public Policy, Vol. 43, Issue 3, 432-450.

Mazzucato, M. (2013) The Entrepreneurial State: Debunking Public vs Private Sector Myths, London: Anthem Press.

Mazzucato M. and Penna C. (2016), ‘The Brazilian Innovation System: A Mission-Orientated Policy Proposal, CGEE

Mazzucato M. (2018), ‘Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union: A problem-solving approach to fuel innovation-led growth’. <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/5b2811d1-16be-11e8-9253-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

Meissner D., Polt, W., Vonortas N. (2017), ‘Towards a broad understanding of innovation and its importance for innovation policy’, Journal of Technology Transfer 42, 1184-1211.

Monsonís-Payá I., García-Melón M., Lozano J., (2017), ‘Indicators for responsible Research and Innovation: a Methodological Proposal for Context-Based weighting’, Sustainability, 9, 2168

Mytelka L. and Smith K (2002), ‘Policy learning and innovation theory: an interactive and co-evolving process’ Research Policy, 31, 1467-1479.

OECD Glossary of Statistical Terms Online at: <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=6278>

OECD (1997), National Innovation Systems Online at: <https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/2101733.pdf>

OECD (1999), Managing National Innovation Systems, Paris

OECD (2004), ‘Second workshop on Composite Indicators of Country Performance, OECD, Paris Online at: <http://www.oecd.org/sti/ind/29398640.pdf>

OECD (2005) ‘Oslo Manual: Guidelines for Collecting and Interpreting Innovation Data’, 3rd Edition, The Measurement of Scientific and Technological Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris

OECD (2015) 'Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for collecting and reporting data on research and experimental development', The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris

Oliver, K., Lorenc, T., Innvær, S. (2014), 'New directions in evidence-based policy research: a critical analysis of the literature', Health Research Policy and Systems, 12:34

Poel M., Schroeder R., Treperman J., Rubinstein, M., Meyer, E., Mahieu, B., Scholten, C., and Svetachova M. (2015) 'Data for Policy: A study of big data and other innovative data-driven approaches for evidence-informed policymaking

Rafols I., Ciarli, T., Van Zwanenberg, P., Stirling, A. (2012), 'Towards indicators for 'opening up' science and technology policy' Online at: <http://ipp.oii.ox.ac.uk/sites/ipp/files/documents/Rafols-Ciarli-OpeningUp-FULL.pdf>

Results for America (2017), 'A Landscape Review: 100+ Government Mechanisms to advance the Use of data and evidence in Policymaking, http://results4america.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/Landscape_int_FINAL.pdf

Santamaría L., Nieto M., Barge-Gil, A. (2009), 'beyond formal R&D: Taking advantage of other sources of innovation in low- and medium-technology industries', Research Policy 38, pp. 507-517.

Shaxson L., (2005), 'Is your evidence robust enough? Questions for policy makers and practitioners', Evidence & Policy, Vol. 1, No. 1, 101-111.

Sindi website: social media supported innovation indicators Online at: <http://hlab.ee.tut.fi/sindi/social-media-supported-innovation-indicators.html>

Simeth M., Cincera, M. (2016), 'Corporate Science, Innovation, and Firm Value', Management Science, 62(7), 1970-1981.

Simeth, M., Raffo, J. D. (2013). 'What makes companies pursue an open science strategy?' Research Policy, 42(9), 1531-1543.

Sivertsen, G., (2010), A Performance Indicator based on Complete Data for the Scientific Publication Output at Research Institutions, ISSI NEWSLETTER VOL. 6. NR. 1., 22-28.

Still, K., Isomursu, M., Koskela-Huotari, K., Huhtamäki, J. (2011), 'Social media-supported indicators for user-driven service innovation', VTT Symposium on Service Innovation, <http://www.vtt.fi/inf/pdf/symposiums/2011/S271.pdf>, 208-217.

Still K., Huhtamäki, J., Russel M., Rubens N., (2012), 'Paradigm shift in innovation indicators—from analog to digital', 5th ISPIM Innovation Symposium, Seoul, Korea

Strehlenert H., Richter-Sundberg L., Nyström M.E., Hasson H., (2015), 'Evidence-informed policy formulation and implementation: a comparative case study of two national policies for improving health and social care in Sweden', Implementation Science, 10:169, pp. 1-10

Swann P., (2010), 'The Economics of Standardization: An Update', Report for the UK Department of Business, Innovation and Skills (BIS)

Teirlinck P., Delanghe, H., Padilla, P., Verbeek, A. (2013), 'Closing the policy cycle: Increasing the utilization of evaluation findings in research, technological development and innovation policy design', *Science and Public Policy* 40, 366–377.

Torrì, S., Gambardella, A., Giuri, P., Harhoff, D., Hoisl, K., & Mariani, M. (2016). Used, blocking and sleeping patents: Empirical evidence from a large-scale inventor survey. *Research Policy*, 45(7), 1374–1385.

Wieczorek A.J., Hekkert M.P. (2012), 'Systemic instruments for systemic innovation problems: A framework for policy makers and innovation scholars', *Science and Public Policy*, Vol. 39, Issue 1, 74-87.